

Synthesis and molluscicidal activity of 6-carboethoxy-(2-substituted)-1,3,4-thia/oxadiazolo[2,3-*b*]pyrimidin-5-ones and 5-amino-(2-substituted)-1,3,4-thia/oxadiazolo[2,3-*b*]pyrimidin-7-ones

Ashutosh Singh and Nizamuddin *

Agro Chemical Research Laboratory, Chemistry Department, D. D. U. Gorakhpur University,
Gorakhpur-273 009, India

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Several 6-carboethoxy-(2-substituted)-1,3,4-thia/oxadiazolo[2,3-*b*]pyrimidin-5-ones **3** and **6** and 5-amino-(2-substituted)-1,3,4-thia/oxadiazolo[2,3-*b*]pyrimidin-7-ones **4** and **7** have been synthesised from the synthon 2-amino-(5-substituted)-1,3,4-thia/oxadiazoles **1** and diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate and ethyl cyanoacetate respectively. The molluscicidal activity of few title compounds have been evaluated against snail *Lymnaea accuminata*.

In continuation of our work on fused heterocycles like triazolo-thiadiazoles¹⁻³, oxadiazolo-thiazoles⁴, thiadiazolo-thiazoles⁵, thiadiazolo-quinazolones⁶, oxadiazolo-indoles⁷ and in view of the biological importance of 1,3,4-thia/oxadiazoles⁸⁻¹⁰ ring and pyrimidine ring¹¹⁻¹³, we wish to report herein the synthesis of another fused heterocyclic systems thia/oxadiazolo-pyrimidine-5-ones **3** and **6** and thia/oxadiazolo-pyrimidin-7-ones **4** and **7** with biological interest. The investigation was found to be of further interest because compactness and planarity of such ring system may be an additional factor for enhancing other biological activities as it does with herbicidal, fungicidal, antiallergic and inflammation inhibitory activities. The required synthon 2-amino-5-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared according to known methods^{14,15}. When these amino oxa/thiadiazoles were allowed to react with diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate at 130°C, furnished (2-substituted)-5-(*N*-2,2-dicarboethoxyethene)amino-1,3,4-thia/oxadiazoles **2** and **5** respectively. That the exo-amino nitrogen and not one of the ring nitrogens was alkylated was supported by ¹H NMR spectrum of **2** and **5**. Heating of **2** and **5** in diphenylether at 250°C, furnished title compounds **3** and **6**. Structure of **2** and **5** was confirmed by their IR and ¹H NMR spectra. Presence of NH peak in IR and ¹H NMR spectra of **2** and **5** and its absence in **3** and **6** confirmed the cyclization of **2** and **5** into **3** and **6** respectively. On the otherhand heating of **1** with ethyl cyanoacetate and ammonium acetate at 140°C, furnished the title compounds **4** and **7** (Scheme 1). The presence of C=O peak in IR spectra of **4** and **7** along with ¹H NMR and mass spectra confirmed the formation of **4** and **7**. The characterization data of all compounds is given in Table 1.

Results and discussion

The molluscicidal data indicates that all tested compounds showed strong to moderate activities. The molluscicidal activity of all the tested compound is dose and time dependent. Compound **4d** (24 h, LC₅₀.09) has greater molluscicidal activity than other compounds (**3d**, **6c**, **7c**). This clearly indicates that thiadiazolo pyrimidinone system with amino group has greater activity than other comparable systems. Presence of amino group in pyrimidine ring increases activity many fold. Molluscicidal activity depends on the nature of substituents also for the same system. The electron donating substituents such as methyl, methoxy group enhanced the molluscicidal activity. On the other hand the electron withdrawing substituents such as chloro decreased the molluscicidal activity.

The slope values were steep and separate estimation of LC₅₀ based on each of the six replicates were found to be within the 95% confidence limits of LC₅₀. The steep slope values indicated that even small increase in the concentration causes a higher mortality in snails. The *t* ratio is greater than 1.96 which indicates that regression is significant. Values of heterogeneity factor less than 1 denote that in the replicate test of random sample, the concentration response lines would fall within 95% confidence limits and thus the model fits the data adequately. The index of significance of potency estimation, *g* value, indicates that the value of the mean is within the limits at all probability (90, 95, 99) as *t* is less than 0.5.

Experimental

Procedure for one representative case for each step has been described. Melting points were taken in open glass

Table I. Characterisation data for compounds 2a-f, 3a-f, 4a-f, 5a-d, 6a-d and 7a-d

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Mol. formula	Found (calcd.)%			IR (KBr) ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}			$^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) (δ , ppm)
					C	H	N	-NH ₂	-NH	C=O	
2a	2-CH ₃	60	118	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅ S	54.8 (55.2)	5.1 5.4	10.1 10.7	-	3245	1730	1.3 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.1 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 6.6–7.7 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.6 (1H, d, NH)
2b	3-CH ₃	52	80	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅ S	55.1 (55.2)	4.8 5.4	10.0 10.7	-	3230	1715	1.2 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.6 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.1 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 6.9–7.6 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.4 (1H, d, NH)
2c	4-CH ₃	60	112	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅ S	54.6 (55.2)	5.3 5.4	10.3 10.7	-	3240	1720	1.2 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.7 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.3 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 7.0–7.9 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.4 (1H, d, NH)
2d	4-Cl	59	110	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₅ SCl	49.2 (49.6)	4.0 4.4	10.0 10.2	-	3250	1725	1.4 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 3.6 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.1 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 6.8–7.9 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.5 (1H, d, NH)
2e	4-Cl, 3-CH ₃	61	123	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₅ SCl	50.3 (50.8)	4.3 4.7	9.1 9.9	-	3230	1730	1.2 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.3 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 6.7–7.9 (3H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.6 (1H, d, NH)
2f	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	58	103	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ S	56.0 (56.3)	5.3 5.7	10.1 10.4	-	3240	1715	1.4 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 2.3 (6H, s, 2 × CH ₃), 3.6 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.1 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 7.1–8.1 (3H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.5 (1H, d, NH)
3a	2-CH ₃	56	165	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	55.2 (55.7)	4.0 4.3	12.1 12.2	-	1730, 1655		1.2 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.7 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.4 (4H, q, CH ₂), 6.8–8.1 (5H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
3b	3-CH ₃	60	100	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	55.4 (55.7)	3.8 4.3	12.0 12.2	-	1740, 1650		1.4 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.6 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.1 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.6–7.9 (5H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
3c	4-CH ₃	53	110	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	54.9 (55.7)	3.7 4.3	11.9 12.2	-	1750, 1645		1.2 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.1 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.8–8.1 (5H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
3d	4-Cl	57	105	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₄ SCl	49.1 (49.2)	2.9 3.3	11.4 11.5	-	1740, 1660		1.4 (3H, t, CH ₃), 3.6 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.2 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.9–7.9 (5H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
3e	4-Cl, 3-CH ₃	55	157	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄ SCl	50.3 (50.5)	3.2 3.7	10.7 11.1	-	1710, 1650		1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.6 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.4 (2H, q, OCH ₂), 4.4 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.8–8.1 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
3f	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	60	173	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	56.3 (56.8)	4.3 4.7	10.9 11.7	-	1745, 1655		1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.3 (6H, s, 2 × CH ₃), 3.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.1 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.8–7.9 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
4a	2-CH ₃	58	160	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	54.0 (54.1)	4.0 4.2	19.1 19.4	3390	-	1690	2.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.7 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.8–8.1 (5H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.1 (2H, b, NH ₂)
4b	3-CH ₃	59	103	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	53.7 (54.1)	3.9 4.2	19.3 19.4	3360	-	1685	2.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.9–8.0 (5H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.1 (2H, b, NH ₂)
4c	4-CH ₃	61	218	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	53.9 (54.1)	3.7 4.2	18.5 19.4	3380	-	1670	2.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.6 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 7.0–8.2 (5H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.2 (2H, b, NH ₂)
4d	4-Cl	53	160	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	46.5 (46.7)	2.8 2.9	17.8 18.1	3395	-	1675	3.7 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.9–8.0 (5H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.5 (2H, b, NH ₂)
4e	4-Cl, 3-CH ₃	57	175	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	47.9 (48.4)	3.3 3.4	17.0 17.4	3370	-	1680	2.1 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.7 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.8–8.9 (4H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.4 (2H, b, NH ₂)
4f	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	55	153	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	53.3 (53.6)	3.9 4.6	18.1 18.5	3365	-	1685	2.2 (6H, s, 2 × CH ₃), 3.8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.6–7.2 (4H, m, ArH and C ₆ H)
5a	H	60	81	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	57.6 (58.0)	4.6 5.1	12.1 12.7	-	3240	1720	1.3 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 4.2 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 6.6–7.6 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.4 (1H, d, NH)
5b	2-Cl	55	99	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	52.5 (52.2)	4.1 4.1	11.5 10.6	-	3250	1715	1.2 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 4.2 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 6.7–7.9 (4H, m, ArH), 8.6 (1H, d, NH)
5c	4-Cl	52	108	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₅ Cl	52.1 (52.5)	4.0 4.4	11.3 11.5	-	3240	1730	1.3 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 4.1 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 7.0–8.2 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.5 (1H, d, NH)
5d	4-OCH ₃	58	161	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₆	54.1 (56.5)	5.1 5.3	11.1 11.6	-	3245	1725	1.4 (6H, t, 2 × CH ₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.2 (4H, q, 2 × CH ₂), 6.8–8.3 (4H, m, ArH and C ₇ H), 8.6 (1H, d, NH)
6a	H	56	101	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	58.3 (58.5)	3.6 3.9	14.8 15.2	-	1740, 1650		1.2 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.3 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.9–8.0 (6H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
6b	2-Cl	61	107	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	51.7 (52.0)	2.8 3.2	12.6 13.5	-	1760, 1670		1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.1 (2H, q, CH ₂), 7.0–8.1 (5H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
6c	4-Cl	47	195	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	51.4 (52.0)	2.6 3.2	13.1 13.5	-	1755, 1650		1.1 (3H, t, CH ₃), 4.4 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.9–7.8 (5H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
6d	4-OCH ₃	57	160	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄	56.7 (57.1)	3.6 4.1	13.1 13.3	-	1745, 1650		1.4 (3H, t, CH ₃), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.2 (2H, q, CH ₂), 6.8–8.9 (6H, m, ArH and C ₇ H)
7a	H	50	123	C ₁₃ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂	57.1 (57.8)	3.1 3.5	24.3 24.5	3380	-	1685	6.9–7.9 (6H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.4 (2H, b, NH ₂)
7b	2-Cl	55	141	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	49.7 (50.2)	2.4 2.7	20.9 21.3	3370	-	1675	6.7–8.1 (5H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.3 (2H, b, NH ₂)
7c	4-Cl	53	174	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	49.5 (50.2)	2.6 2.7	21.1 21.3	3390	-	1680	6.9–7.6 (5H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.3 (2H, b, NH ₂)
7d	4-OCl ₃	61	163	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃	55.1 (55.8)	3.6 3.9	21.4 21.7	3385	-	1685	3.9 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.8–7.9 (5H, m, ArH and C ₆ H), 8.4 (2H, b, NH ₂)

tained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from ethanol, yield 1.6 g (58%), m.p. 160°C; IR (KBr) 3390 (NH₂), 1690 (C=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.7 (2H, s, OCH₂), 6.8–8.1 (5H, m, ArH and C₆H), 8.1 (2H, b, NH₂).

The other compounds **4b-f** were similarly prepared and their physical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-5-(N-2,2-dicarboethoxyethene)amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole (5a) : A mixture of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.04 mol) and diethyl ethoxymethylenemalonate (0.046 mol) was heated at 130°C for 3 h. Ethanol was distilled off from the reaction during this time. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice. The solid thus obtained was washed with water and crystallized from ethanol, yield 7.9 g (60%), m.p. 81°C; IR (KBr) 3240 (N–H), 1720 (C=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.3 (6H, t, 2 × CH₃), 4.2 (4H, q, 2 × CH₂), 7.6–7.7 (4H, m, ArH and C₇H), 8.6 (1H, d, NH); MS *m/z* 331 (M⁺), 332 (M+1), 333 (M+2).

The other compounds **5b-d** were similarly prepared and their physical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-6-carboethoxy-1,3,4-oxadiazolo-[2,3-*b*]pyrimidine-5-one (6a) : 2-Phenyl-5-(N-2,2-dicarboethoxyethene)amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole **5a** (3.31 g, 0.01 M) was refluxed in diphenylether (10 mL). The solvent was removed by distillation *in vacuo* and the residue poured into ice. The solid thus obtained was washed with water and crystallized from ethanol, yield 1.5 g (56%), m.p. 101°C; IR (KBr) 1740, 1650 (C=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.3 (4H, q, CH₂), 6.8–8.1 (5H, m, ArH and C₇H); MS *m/z* 311 (M⁺), 312 (M+1), 313 (M+2).

The other compounds **6b-d** were similarly prepared and their physical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

5-Amino-2-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolo[2,3-*b*]pyrimidine-7-one (7a) : A mixture of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (1.61 g, 0.01 M), ethyl cyanoacetate (6.61 g, 0.08 M) was heated at 150°C for 3 h. Dioxan (20 mL) was added to the flask and refluxed for 3 h. Solvent was removed by distillation and residue was poured into ice. The mass thus obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from ethanol, yield 1.1 g (50%), m.p. 123°C; IR (KBr) 3380 (NH₂), 1685 (C=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 6.9–7.9 (6H, m, ArH and C₆H), 8.4 (2H, b, NH₂); MS *m/z* 228 (M⁺), 229 (M+1), 230 (M+2).

The other compounds **7b-d** were similarly prepared and their physical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

Evaluation of molluscicidal activity :

The molluscicidal activity of compounds of types **3, 4, 6**

and **7** evaluated against the snail *Lymnaea acuminata* which is a vector of giant liver flukes. *Fasciola gigantica* and *Fasciola hepatica*. It caused endemic fasciolosis in cattle population of eastern Uttar Pradesh. Being herbivorous, these snails cause damage to submerged paddy crops especially in "Terai" region of U.P. In this region the water reservoirs and submerged paddy fields have become foci for such snail pests.

Adult *L. acuminata* (2.25 ± 0.20 cm in length) were collected from ponds, lakes and low lying submerged fields and were used as test animals. The snails were acclimatized for 72 h in laboratory condition. Six sets of glass aquarium were used for each concentration of experiment. Ten adult snails were kept in each glass aquaria containing 3L dechlorinated tap water. Toxicity of different compounds were determined, by the method of Rao and Singh¹⁶. The snails were treated with different concentrations of compounds taken. Mortality was recorded 24 h interval upto 96 h exposure periods. Control animals were kept in a similar manner without treatment. Dead snails were removed from the aquarium to avoid contamination of water. No response to the needle probe confirmed the death of the snail.

For the one compound of each type (**3d, 4d, 6c, 7c** arbitrarily chosen) LC₅₀ values, lower and upper confidence limits (LCL and UCL), *g* values, *t*-ratio values, slope values and heterogeneity values were calculated according to the method of Polo computer programme of Rusell *et al.*¹⁷ (Table 2).

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Singh *et al.* : Synthesis and molluscicidal activity of 6-carboethoxy(2-substituted)- *etc.*

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